

Dose Intensity for Oncology Clinical Trials

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Abstract

Dose intensity (DI) is a widely used measure of drug exposure in clinical trials. The magnitude of DI is linked to drug toxicity, tolerability, and treatment adherence. DI can be expressed as observed, planned, and relative dose intensity (RDI). In oncology trials, modifying dose (through reduction or interruption) is an effective way to manage drug toxicity. Managing toxicity and maintaining a high RDI are crucial for achieving better response and treatment outcomes. Calculating RDI can be complex, especially in the context of ramp-up dosing and dose modification due to drug-drug interaction. DI and RDI are included in the FDA Office of Oncology Drug Safety Data Standard Request. Sponsors of oncology trials seeking marketing approval, especially expedited approval, should ensure their analysis datasets present DI and RDI appropriately presented and with clear traceability to the collected data.

This paper introduces different methods of calculating RDI, and their associated nuances. It represents DI and RDI in a mock-up exposure analysis dataset, followed by recommendations on optimal data collection for analyzing dose intensity in clinical trials.

Key Words: Relative Dose Intensity, oncology clinical trials, data analysis, data collection

1. Introduction

Dose intensity, a measure of the drug given per unit of time during treatment, has gained importance in evaluating drug exposure. The planned dose intensity (PDI) is determined by the treatment schedule outlined in the study protocol. Conversely, the observed dose intensity (ODI) is calculated for each subject who received the study drug, considering the actual dose administered and duration of drug administration.

In a simple scenario of continuous daily dosing, such as when a study drug is administered at a daily dose of 40 mg until treatment discontinuation:

- The PDI would be 40 mg/day.
- The ODI can be calculated by dividing the total actual dose administered over the treatment duration by the actual treatment duration.
- The relative dose intensity (RDI) is defined as the ratio of ODI to PDI, expressed as a percentage.

In this example, an RDI of 100% indicates that the planned dose was administered each day as scheduled during the treatment period. If a subject skipped doses and the ODI is lower than the PDI, the RDI will be less than 100%. Conversely, if a subject receives overdose and the ODI is higher than the PDI, the RDI will be greater than 100%.

1.1 Importance of Relative Dose Intensity in Oncology Trials

As early as the 1980s, studies began examining the correlation between dose intensity and chemotherapy response [1]. A systematic review of patients with metastatic lung, breast, or ovarian cancer receiving chemotherapy between January 2000 and April 2013 found that maintaining an RDI of $\geq 85\%$ had a favorable impact on survival [2]. Recent reviews, such as Nielsen CM's 2021 study [3], have also indicated longer overall survival (OS) with RDI $\geq 80\%$ or $\geq 85\%$ for both regimens, implying that managing toxicities across treatment modalities may contribute to higher RDI maintenance and better survival outcomes for patients with advanced solid tumors. Other oncology treatments, such as immunotherapy and molecularly targeted agents, have also been studied for their RDI correlation with better response [4, 5, and 6].

1.2 Dose intensity in FDA guidance

In January 2023, the FDA released draft guidance titled “Optimizing the dosage of human prescription drugs and biological products for the treatment of oncology diseases”. This guidance recommends identifying the optimal dosage and assessing safety and tolerability across multiple dosages, both of which involve dose intensity. The FDA Oncology Center of Excellence's [Oncology Dosing Tool Kit](#) also lists relative dose intensity as a key safety information area to support dosage optimization.

1.3 FDA OOD safety data standard request

The FDA Office of Oncologic Diseases (OOD) oversees development, approval, and regulation of drug and biologic treatments for cancer and hematologic malignancies. The [OOD Safety standard data specifications](#), which outlines the format of safety datasets submitted to the FDA, is referenced in the Standard Operating Procedures section of the FDA OCE [Real-Time Oncology Review \(RTOR\)](#). The RTOR program is granted to NDA applications that meet specific criteria, with one criterion being drugs likely to demonstrate substantial improvements over available therapy or meet criteria for Expedited Programs. Sponsors submitting complete ADaM dataset packages in the RTOR program for pivotal studies are expected to follow the OOD Safety Standard Data Specifications for the requested format of safety datasets.

In the next section, we will use the OOD Safety Standard Data Specifications to outline different scenarios for deriving dose intensity.

2. Methods for Calculating Dose Intensity (DI)

As stated in the Introduction (Section 1), the calculation of PDI, ODI, RDI necessitates specific information, including the total actual dose administered, total planned dose, planned treatment duration, and actual treatment duration. In the context of oncology studies, dosing is administered in cycles, with a common planned duration of 4 weeks or 28 days, resulting in treatment repetition every 28 days. However, the actual length of cycles may vary within a specified range due to factors such as dose intolerance or logistic reasons, as outlined in the study protocol. It is also possible for a cycle to be shorter if the treatment is interrupted at the end of the observation period.

In the upcoming sections, we will outline the various methods for calculating dose intensity in different settings. It is important to note that all data used in this paper are mock-up data, purposefully simplified to highlight the calculation of dose intensity. For example, a fixed planned cycle length of 28 days is used, and adjustments based on patient weight are not taken into consideration due to the application of unit-based dosing.

According to the FDA [OOD Safety standard data specifications](#), two ADaM (Analysis Data Model) datasets, namely ADEX and ADEXSUM, are recommended to support all analysis related to the study drug exposure. The input data for dose intensity calculation can be found in the ADEX dataset, while the derivation parameters are included in the ADEXSUM dataset. For each specific setting described later in this paper, a mini ADEX dataset containing two subjects is utilized, with only the necessary variables included to explain the calculation of dose intensity.

Dataset and variable metadata:

ADEX: Exposure Analysis Dataset

Structure: One record per subject per treatment (EXTRT) per visit / dose interval

Variable Name	Variable Label	Type	Codelist/ Controlled Terms	Source Derivation Notes
USUBJID	Unique Subject Identifier	Char		SDTM.EX
EXTRT	Name of Treatment	Char		SDTM.EX
EXDOSE	Dose	Num		SDTM.EX
EXDOSEU	Dose Units	Char	UNIT	SDTM.EX
EXSTDY	Study Day of Start of Treatment	Num		SDTM.EX

Variable Name	Variable Label	Type	Codelist/ Controlled Terms	Source Derivation Notes
EXENDY	Study Day of End of Treatment	Num		SDTM.EX
EXDURD	Duration of Treatment (days)	Num		Derived treatment duration (days)
EXROUTE	Route of Administration	Char	ROUTE	SDTM.EX
EXADJ	Reason for Dose Adjustment	Char		SDTM.EX
VISIT	Visit Name	Char		SDTM.EX

2.1 DI calculation for intermittently administered study drug

The table below illustrates two subjects' actual study drug exposure in the chronological order. The subjects are scheduled to receive 20 mg or 40mg of intravenous treatment of A001 on day 1 of each 28-day cycle.

2.1.1 ADEX

USUBJID	EXTRT	VISIT	EXDOSE	EXDOSEU	EXSTDY	EXROUTE	EXADJ
12345001	A001	Cycle 1 Day 1	20	mg	1	INTRAVENOUS	
12345001	A001	Cycle 2 Day 1	20	mg	29	INTRAVENOUS	
12345001	A001	Cycle 3 Day 1	20	mg	57	INTRAVENOUS	
12345001	A001	Cycle 4 Day 1	20	mg	85	INTRAVENOUS	
12345001	A001	Cycle 5 Day 1	20	mg	113	INTRAVENOUS	
12345001	A001	Cycle 6 Day 1	20	mg	141	INTRAVENOUS	
12345002	A001	Cycle 1 Day 1	40	mg	1	INTRAVENOUS	
12345002	A001	Cycle 2 Day 1	40	mg	29	INTRAVENOUS	
12345002	A001	Cycle 3 Day 1	40	mg	65	INTRAVENOUS	Adverse event
12345002	A001	Cycle 4 Day 1	40	mg	100	INTRAVENOUS	Adverse event
12345002	A001	Cycle 5 Day 1	40	mg	134	INTRAVENOUS	Adverse event
12345002	A001	Cycle 6 Day 1	40	mg	162	INTRAVENOUS	

2.1.2 Calculation of PDI, ODI and RDI

In comparison to the simple example provided in the Introduction (section 1), the calculations for PDI, ODI, and RDI in this example are similar in two aspects:

1. The PDI is pre-specified, set at 20 mg/cycle for subject 12345001 and 40 mg/cycle for subject 12345002.
2. the ODI can be derived by dividing the total actual dose amount by the total actual treatment duration, using the same unit as PDI

The difference lies in the calculation of the total actual treatment duration. In the previous example, it was computed as the difference between the last dose date and the first dose date, plus 1. However, in this example, we incorporate the dose frequency by using "+28" instead of "+1". The variable EXSTDY is calculated as the difference between the dose date and the date of the first dose, plus 1. Consequently, the total actual treatment duration is obtained by subtracting 1 from the EXSTDY of the last dose (162) and adding 28, measured in days.

For subject 12345001:

- The ODI is calculated as $20 * 6 / ((141 - 1 + 28) / 28) = 20$ (mg/cycle).

- The RDI is determined as $ODI / PDI = 20 / 20 = 100\%$.

For subject 12345002:

- The ODI is computed as $40 * 6 / ((162 - 1 + 28) / 28) = 35.6$ (mg/cycle).

- The RDI is calculated as $35.6 / 40 = 88.9\%$.

2.1.3 Interpreting RDI Results

Subject 12345001 has an RDI of 100%, indicating that the subject received the planned dose in its entirety. This suggests good compliance with the dosing schedule and a high tolerance to potential toxicity.

On the other hand, subject 12345002 had an RDI of 88.9%, reflecting a reduced dose intensity. In this case, Cycle 6 was delayed until study day 162, resulting in a 21-day deviation from the scheduled cycle. This delay is evident from the EXSTDY values for cycles 3, 4, and 5, exceeding 28 days since the most recent cycle. The reason for the cycle delay is indicated as an "adverse event" based on the EXADJ variable. This safety issue or dose intolerance could potentially impact the treatment's effectiveness.

2.2 DI calculation for study drug planned administered partially in a cycle, accounting for dose interruption

In some studies, a study treatment may be administered only for a portion of a treatment cycle and then not administered for the rest of the cycle, resulting in an on-and-off pattern during the entire treatment period. In the following example for a combination therapy setting, one treatment is planned to be administered for the first 5 days only in a 28-day cycle.

2.2.1 ADEX

USUBJID	EXTRT	VISIT	EXDOSE	EXDOSEU	EXSTDY	EXROUTE
12345020	B001	Cycle 1 Day 1	20	mg	1	SUBCUTANEOUS
12345020	B001	Cycle 1 Day 2	20	mg	2	SUBCUTANEOUS
12345020	B001	Cycle 1 Day 3	20	mg	3	SUBCUTANEOUS
12345020	B001	Cycle 1 Day 4	20	mg	4	SUBCUTANEOUS
12345020	B001	Cycle 1 Day 5	20	mg	5	SUBCUTANEOUS
12345020	B001	Cycle 2 Day 1	20	mg	35	SUBCUTANEOUS
12345020	B001	Cycle 2 Day 2	20	mg	36	SUBCUTANEOUS
12345020	B001	Cycle 2 Day 3	20	mg	37	SUBCUTANEOUS
12345020	B001	Cycle 2 Day 5	20	mg	39	SUBCUTANEOUS

2.2.2 Calculation of PDI, ODI and RDI

In this example,

- The PDI is 100 mg per 28-day cycle or 20 mg/day in the 5-day treatment period in each cycle.
- The ODI calculation is adjusted to compute the treatment duration for each cycle before adding up the numbers. For subject 12345020, the treatment duration is 5 days in both cycle 1 and 2. The total dose is $20 * 9 = 180$ mg. Therefore, the ODI is calculated as $180 / 10 = 18$ mg/day.
- The RDI is calculated as $18 / 20 = 90\%$

2.2.3 Interpreting RDI results

The calculated RDI of 90% is due to the skipped dose on Cycle 2 Day 4. This approach is referred to as “accounting for dose interruption”, where the dose interruption within the cycle is taken into account. It is worth noting that the calculation of ODI and RDI would differ if the cycle delay were factored in, as seen in the delay of cycle 2 in this example.

2.3 DI calculation for daily, continuous study drug with stepwise dosing, cycle interruption and cycle delay

2.3.1 ADEX

The table below depicts a subject’s actual study drug exposure in chronological order. The study utilizes stepwise dosing, starting from 100 mg on Cycle 1 Day 1, increasing to 200 mg on Cycle 1 Day 2 and 400 mg from Cycle 1 Day 3 and later doses. The planned cycle length is 28 days. The subject experienced a delay in starting cycle 2, dose interruption before completing cycle 2, and a similar cycle delay and dose interruption in cycle 3. In cycle 4, the dose was reduced from 400 mg to 200 mg.

EXSTDY and EXENDY indicate the study day of the start and end of a dosing interval, respectively.

USUBJID	EXTRT	VISIT	EXDOSE	EXDOSEU	EXSTDY	EXENDY	EXROUTE	EXDURD
20001001	A002	Cycle 1 Day 1	100	mg	1	1	Oral	1
20001001	A002	Cycle 1 Day 2	200	mg	2	2	Oral	1
20001001	A002	Cycle 1 Day 3	400	mg	3	28	Oral	26
20001001	A002	Cycle 2	400	mg	37	56	Oral	20
20001001	A002	Cycle 3	400	mg	71	86	Oral	16
20001001	A002	Cycle 4	400	mg	106	109	Oral	4
20001001	A002	Cycle 4	200	mg	110	126	Oral	17

2.3.2 Calculation of PDI, ODI and RDI

The total actual dose is calculated as $(100 + 200 + 400 * 26) + 400 * 20 + 400 * 16 + 400 * 4 + 200 * 17 = 30100$ mg. The total actual treatment duration is 126 days.

In this setting, the PDI is not a predetermined amount as the dose amount is higher after the first three days of treatment. The ODI is calculated as $30100 / 126 = 238.9$ mg/day.

The planned total dose can be calculated with different approaches.

- One approach assumes each cycle started exactly 28 days after the previous one. $126 / 28 = 28 * 4 + 14$ meaning the subject could have completed 4 full cycles and a partial cycle of 14 days (cycle 5).
 - The planned total dose in the 126-day treatment duration would be: $(100 + 200 + 400 * 26) + 400 * 28 + 400 * 28 + 400 * 28 + 400 * 14 = 49900$ mg.
 - The RDI is $30100 / 49900 = 60.3\%$.
- Another approach does not take into account cycle delay.
 - This subject is on day 21 of cycle 4 (EXSTDY 126- 106 +1). The planned total dose would be $(100 + 200 + 400 * 26) + 400 * 28 + 400 * 28 + 400 * 21 = 41500$ mg.
 - The RDI would be $30100 / 41500 = 72.5\%$.

2.3.3 Interpreting RDI results

This example shows how the RDI can differ depending on the algorithm applied. Statisticians and analysts must use the approach that makes the most scientific and statistical sense. It is important to interpret the data in the context of the algorithm or assumption used.

It is worth noting that the calculation of treatment duration explained in Section 2.2 may be utilized for this setting, resulting in a different approach to this scenario. With that approach, the total actual and planned treatment duration comprises of multiple pieces formed by breaking the whole treatment duration into multiple within-cycle interruptions and between-cycle interruptions (cycle delay). The total planned dose will be calculated based on the planned single dose and the actual treatment duration.

2.4 DI calculation for daily, continuous study drug with dose modification due to drug-drug interaction

In previous examples, the planned dose for a single administration is a predetermined amount specified in the protocol, although there may be dose reductions or withholding based on protocol specified criteria or due to logistic reasons. This section addresses a scenario in which the effect of a study treatment is modified by concomitant medication and therefore needs to be considered in the calculation of dose intensity.

Many oral anticancer drugs are metabolized by CYP3A. Cancer patients may be prescribed concomitant medication that are substrates, inducers, or inhibitors of CYP3A. CYP3A inhibitors amplify the effect of these anticancer drugs while CYP3A inducers reduce the effect of these anticancer drugs. According to the FDA document “Acute Myeloid Leukemia (AML): Developing Drugs and Biological Products for Treatment”, released in October 2022, patients with AML are commonly prescribed concomitant medication that are substrates, inducers, or inhibitors of cytochrome P450 (CYP) enzymes. In particular, triazole antifungals are moderate to strong CYP3A inhibitors commonly prescribed to reduce the risk of invasive fungal infections in patients with AML. Such drugs may increase the systemic exposure of new AML drugs that are metabolized by CYP3A and may decrease the tolerability of new AML drugs that are CYP3A substrates. If a drug used to treat AML is a CYP3A substrate, the protocol should specify dose modification rules in the context of concomitant use of moderate and strong CYP3A substrates. The following section explains how to calculate the total planned dose or total actual dose adjusted by the CYP3A inhibitor use for the purpose of calculating RDI.

2.4.1 ADEX

In the example below. The study drug “A003” has a drug-drug interaction with CYP3A inhibitors. According to the study protocol, the dose of “A003” should be reduced from 200 mg to 100 mg when a moderate CYP3A inhibitor is administered concomitantly, and the dose should be further reduced to 50 mg when a strong CYP3A inhibitor is administered. The value of variable CYP3AI indicates whether CYP3A inhibitor was used and whether it was moderate or strong, if used.

USUBJID	EXTRT	VISIT	EXDOSE	EXDOSEU	EXSTDY	EXENDY	EXDURD	CYP3AI
20001011	A003	Cycle 1	200	mg	1	28	28	no
20001011	A003	Cycle 2	200	mg	29	39	11	no
20001011	A003	Cycle 2	100	mg	40	56	17	moderate
20001011	A003	Cycle 3	100	mg	57	63	7	strong
20001011	A003	Cycle 3	200	mg	64	84	21	no

2.4.2 Calculation of PDI, ODI and RDI

There are at least two different approaches to calculate dose intensity while considering this drug-drug interaction.

Approach 1: This approach includes adjustments to the planned dose based on the CYP3Ai use, as indicated by the variable DOSADJP. In the second interval of cycle 2, the planned dose should be adjusted to 100 mg due to the co-administration of a moderate CYP3Ai. In the first interval of cycle 3, the planned dose should be adjusted to 50 mg due to the co-administration of a strong CYP3Ai.

USUBJID	EXTRT	VISIT	EXDOSE	EXDOSEU	EXSTDY	EXENDY	EXDURD	CYP3AI	DOSADJP
20001011	A003	Cycle 1	200	mg	1	28	28	no	200
20001011	A003	Cycle 2	200	mg	29	39	11	no	200
20001011	A003	Cycle 2	100	mg	40	56	17	moderate	100
20001011	A003	Cycle 3	100	mg	57	63	7	strong	50
20001011	A003	Cycle 3	200	mg	64	84	21	no	200

Total actual dose = $200 * 28 + 200 * 11 + 100 * 17 + 100 * 7 + 200 * 21 = 14400$ mg

Total planned dose with adjustment for CYP3Ai = $200 * 28 + 200 * 11 + 100 * 7 + 50 * 7 + 200 * 21 = 14050$ mg

RDI = $14400 / 14050 = 102.5\%$

Approach 2: with this approach, the actual dose is converted to dose with the same effect, as represented by the variable DOSADJA. In the second interval of cycle 2, with the co-administration of a moderate CYP3Ai, the actual dose of 100 mg has the effect of 200 mg. In the first interval of cycle 3, with the co-administration of strong CYP3Ai, the actual dose of 100 mg has the effect of 400 mg.

USUBJID	EXTRT	VISIT	EXDOSE	EXDOSEU	EXSTDY	EXENDY	EXDURD	CYP3AI	DOSADJA	DOSP
20001011	A003	Cycle 1	200	mg	1	28	28	no	200	200
20001011	A003	Cycle 2	200	mg	29	39	11	no	200	200
20001011	A003	Cycle 2	100	mg	40	56	17	moderate	200	200
20001011	A003	Cycle 3	100	mg	57	63	7	strong	400	200
20001011	A003	Cycle 3	200	mg	64	84	21	no	200	200

Total actual dose with adjustment for the effect = $200 * 28 + 200 * 11 + 200 * 17 + 400 * 7 + 200 * 21 = 18200$ mg

Total planned dose = $200 * (28 + 11 + 17 + 7 + 21) = 16800$ mg

RDI = $18200 / 16800 = 108.3\%$

2.4.3 Interpreting RDI results

With either of the above approaches, the RDI is above 100%, indicating that the subject received higher dose than planned. This is due to the subject receiving a dose of 100mg instead of the intended 50mg in the first interval of cycle 3 when a strong CYP3A inhibitor was co-administered. The calculated RDI value from the two approaches are slightly different, with a higher value from the second approach due to its higher weight on the incorrect dosing.

It should be noted that the example used in this section was simplified to have each cycle exactly 28 days. When accounting for within-cycle and between-cycle dose interruptions, the calculation of RDI becomes more complex. In such cases, the planned dose on days without an actual dose may be determined using different approaches, but they all need to consider the concomitant use of CYP3A inhibitors.

2.5 DI calculation in the setting of fixed treatment duration

In the previous examples, the planned total dose was calculated based on the actual treatment duration, with or without counting the intervals of dose interruption in the middle. In some publication [2], the planned dose may be calculated based on the intended treatment duration. For example, a certain type of chemotherapy is scheduled to be administered for 6 cycles. The planned dose for each subject will be based on the planned dose for 6 cycles, even if the subject discontinued this treatment early.

2.5.1 ADEX

Using the same data as used in section 2.2.1. Per study design, the subject should receive 6 cycles of treatment, however this subject discontinued the treatment labelled as "B001" after two cycles.

USUBJID	EXTRT	VISIT	EXDOSE	EXDOSEU	EXSTDY	EXROUTE
12345020	B001	Cycle 1 Day 1	20	mg	1	SUBCUTANEOUS
12345020	B001	Cycle 1 Day 2	20	mg	2	SUBCUTANEOUS
12345020	B001	Cycle 1 Day 3	20	mg	3	SUBCUTANEOUS
12345020	B001	Cycle 1 Day 4	20	mg	4	SUBCUTANEOUS
12345020	B001	Cycle 1 Day 5	20	mg	5	SUBCUTANEOUS
12345020	B001	Cycle 2 Day 1	20	mg	35	SUBCUTANEOUS
12345020	B001	Cycle 2 Day 2	20	mg	36	SUBCUTANEOUS
12345020	B001	Cycle 2 Day 3	20	mg	37	SUBCUTANEOUS
12345020	B001	Cycle 2 Day 5	20	mg	39	SUBCUTANEOUS

2.5.2 Calculation of PDI, ODI and RDI

- Total actual dose = 180 mg
- Planned total dose = $20 * 5 * 6 = 600$ mg
- The RDI is calculated as $180 / 600 = 30\%$

2.5.3 Interpreting RDI results

The RDI calculated in this manner is significantly lower than the approach described in section 2.2. This RDI can be considered as a more informative measurement when the intended treatment effect is dependent upon the full course of treatment and early discontinuation of treatment has a substantial impact on the treatment effect, rather than simply indicating drug intolerance.

2.6 DI calculation by dose period and by cycle

If dose changes significantly in different periods of the whole treatment duration, it is meaningful to calculate DI for each period. For example, calculating DI for induction cycles and consolidation cycles separately.

Additionally, DI may be calculated by cycle. DI is commonly calculated for the whole treatment period which makes more sense considering that the concept of DI is more about longer term dose intolerance, and that the cycle delay / between cycle interruption impacts the DI. With that said, DI may be calculated for each cycle. In that case, it is important to define the start and end of each cycle for the purpose of calculating total actual and planned dose, with the consideration of extend and shortened cycles due to drug intolerance, logistic reasons, treatment discontinuation, and data cut for interim analysis.

2.7 Summary of section 2 Methods for Calculating Dose Intensity

In section 2, we have explained several methods for calculating dose intensity. In real-time scenarios, you may encounter a combination of the scenarios we discussed. Specifically, in the context of combination therapy, the ADEX and ADEXSUM datasets, which cover dose intensity calculation, contain data for multiple treatments. Furthermore, additional considerations are necessary when calculating the planned total dose, such as handling incomplete cycles (particularly the last cycle) due to early treatment termination or data cutoff for interim analysis. All of these factors contribute to the complexity of dose intensity calculations.

Overall, accurate calculation of dose intensity is crucial for optimizing new cancer treatments and improving patient outcomes. The choice of method for calculating dose intensity is at the discretion of statisticians and depends on the specific treatment regimen and the availability of data.

3. Discussion: Data collection and DI calculation

3.1 Collection of prescribed dose in CRF and its impact on DI calculation

The collection of prescribed dose for each visit / dose interval in the study drug administration CRF may vary among companies. Some companies do not collect prescribed dose, and when it is collected, the meaning of prescribed dose in the CRF may also differ. One convention, convention A, fills the prescribed dose as the originally assigned dose until it is permanently lowered / raised or if the study drug has been discontinued; temporary dose hold due to adverse events do not affect the value of the prescribed dose. Another convention, convention B, updates the prescribed dose to match the visit-level prescribed dose. For example, in the case of dose reduction or withholding per protocol-specified criteria or investigator decision, the prescribed dose will be modified.

The author's intention is not to comprehensively evaluate all different approaches regarding the collection of prescribed dose for oncology studies. Instead, we limit this assessment to its impact on the dose intensity calculation. Approach A ensures that the collected data is most suitable for DI calculation because the prescribed dose accurately represents the planned dose until the permanent treatment discontinuation. When the prescribed dose from approach B is used as the planned dose for DI calculation, the deviation of relative dose intensity from 100% reflects the compliance rather than drug tolerability.

3.2 Collection of granular details of dose adjustment

In the [OOD Safety standard data specifications](#), "Reason for dose adjustment" (EXADJ) is a required variable for ADEX. Although EXADJ is usually collected in the CRF, it alone does not provide precise information about the type of dose adjustment, which could be dose reduction/increase, cycle delay, or dose interruption/withholding/not administered due to non-compliance or logistic reasons. A few indicator variables (flags) about dose reduction (DOSREDFL), interruption (DOSINTFL) and dose delay (DOSDELFL) are also included in the ADEX dataset conditionally. These indicator variables can be derived in the ADAE dataset by comparing the actual dose at each visit /dose interval with the protocol assigned dose and the dose the subject received in prior visits / dose intervals. However, it is preferable to collect these indicators in the CRF and are cross-verify them with other variables such as EXADJ, dose amount and dose start date. This is especially important when dose adjustment are made due to drug-drug interactions, as it is crucial to flag the dose records in the database and ensure accurate recording of the corresponding concomitant medication that interacts with the study drug. These approaches are critical to ensuring data consistency relevant to the dose intensity calculation, reducing the differences in the calculated results from different methods, and therefore increasing the validity of the calculated dose intensity results.

3.3 Collection of study drug administration data for trials on combination therapy

Combination therapy is more commonly studied in oncology therapeutic area than in others, and the development of data standards for combination therapy in the pharmaceutical / biotech industry is yet to catch up. Companies relatively new to oncology area may not have their company-level data standards/conventions updated immediately to cover the needs of their oncology programs. For example, the data collection of the comparator drug or other components in the combination therapy, which are standard of care, may be collected in the concomitant medication CRF instead of the study treatment administration CRF. This approach of data collection does not enable the necessary data collection for dose intensity calculation and does not allow for cross checking the consistency of dosing schedule across all study treatments in the database.

To meet the increased requirements for optimizing the dose for new oncology drugs, the collection of study drug administration data needs to be more proactively and thoroughly planned to satisfy the needs of evidence generation, as well as the trial conduct.

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